

Characteristic Signatures of Aerospace Nickel-Cadmium Cells on Life-Cycle Testing

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ABSTRACT

NASA-Goddard Spaceflight Center (GSFC) is continuing its long-standing program of life-cycle tests of Nickel-Cadmium (NiCd) cells from various battery cell vendors at the Naval Surface Warfare Center (NSWC) in Crane, Indiana in order to predict on-orbit performance and develop onboard management strategies for both nominal and anomalous batteries. Testing is presently in progress on several packs and different sizes of the two types of NiCd cells currently manufactured by Eagle-Picher Industries, Inc. (EPI). These two designs are the Super© NiCd cell and the Magnum© NiCd cell, the significant difference between the two types being the type of separator material. Anomalous charge voltage divergences have been observed in cells from both designs, particularly at cold temperatures and fairly low depths-of-discharge. A similar divergence has also been observed in the one on-board battery of the LEO SAMPEX (Solar Anomalous Magnetospheric Particle Explorer) spacecraft. This paper illustrates the life-cycle test voltage divergences, shows how they differ from divergences observed on previous life-cycle tests of EPI cells, and report the data from at least one attempt to manage the voltage divergence.

NASA/GSFC continues to monitor the advancement of NiCd cell technologies in the United States and in overseas manufacturers. In the United States, the advanced technology development effort has been lead, for the most part, by Hughes Aircraft Company (HAC) and EPI. Several different design types were manufactured by HAC/EPI in the late 1980's, and small groups of cells from each design type were sent to NSWC-Crane for life-cycle testing. All of these early test cells had a nameplate capacity of 21 Ampere-hour (AH). The successful data obtained from these tests became the foundation for follow-on cell production by EPI and procurement by battery end-users.

In order to characterize the performance of these new technologies, GSFC wrote test plans for the testing of small groups of these cells, and has been monitoring and evaluating test results ranging from initial performance testing through to completion of life-cycle testing. Of particular interest to GSFC were those packs undergoing accelerated test (90-minute orbit) life-cycle regime of 40% Depth-of-Discharge (DOD) at 20 °C, using NASA Standard Voltage/Temperature (V/T) levels. These cell packs are tabulated below by NSWC pack designation, along with the design basis and the number of cells tested.

Table I. EPI Advanced NiCd packs tested at 20 °C and 40% DOD

NSWC Pack #	Number of Cells	Design
6000A	5	Polypropylene/PBI* separator (Magnum© NiCd)
6001A	5	Zircar/Polysulfone
6002A	5	Zircar/PBI*
6003A	8	Zircar/Polysulfone
6006A	8	Zircar/PBI*, with electrolyte additive (Super© NiCd)

* Polybenzimidazole-impregnated

Remarkably, most of the packs completed 5 plus years of life-cycle testing under the accelerated regime, despite the fact that cell voltage divergence began to develop in most of the packs long before testing was terminated. It is noteworthy that the packs did not become unmanageable in terms of charge control when the divergence first appeared. This voltage divergence is graphically illustrated in Figures 1 - 13 of this paper, along with a brief description of each pack history.

Pack 6000A

This pack was removed from testing after 28,721 cycles. The final Charge/Discharge (C/D) ratio was 1.07 at a V/T level of 7.5. The primary reasons for termination of testing were end-of-charge voltage divergence and completion of test objectives. This end-of-charge voltage divergence,

which began after 25,000 cycles, is shown below in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Pack 6000A: Min., max. and average cell end-of-charge and end-of-discharge voltages vs cycle number.

Figure 2. Pack 6000A: Individual cell end-of-charge voltages vs cycle number.

End-of-discharge voltage divergence was also noted in Pack 6000A, beginning about cycle 7,000. After the V/T level adjustment at about cycle 17,000, the magnitude of the voltage divergence decreased to a nominal level. Figure 3 below illustrates Pack 6000A at cycle 25,000.

Figure 3. Pack 6000A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time.

Pack 6001A

This pack was removed from testing after 28,306 cycles. The final C/D ratio was 1.08 at a V/T level of 7. The primary reasons for termination of testing were low end-of-discharge voltage and completion of test objectives. The pack experienced end-of-discharge voltage divergence from about cycle 16,000 onward. Also, just six months prior to test termination, a minor charge voltage divergence began to develop at the beginning of charge, as illustrated below in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Pack 6001A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time during cycle 25,000.

Pack 6002A

This pack was removed from testing after 25,357 cycles. The final C/D ratio was 1.27 at a V/T level of 7. The primary reasons for termination of testing were high C/D ratios, high end-of-charge voltage divergence and completion of test objectives. The pack experienced both end-of-charge and end-of-discharge voltage divergences from about cycle 16,000 onward. These are illustrated in Figures 5 and 6. The divergence signature for cycle 25,000 is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 5. Pack 6002A: Min., max. and average cell end-of-charge and end-of-discharge voltages vs cycle number.

Figure 6. Individual cell end-of-charge voltages vs cycle number for Pack 6002A.

Figure 7. Pack 6002A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time.

The voltage divergence vs cycle number and time, from cycle 16,000 to 25,000, experienced an extraordinary transformation, as show in Figure 8:

Figure 8. Pack 6002A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle number and time.

Pack 6003A

This pack was removed from testing after 25,217 cycles. The final C/D ratio was 1.11 at a V/T level of 7. The primary reasons for termination of testing were high end-of-charge voltage divergence and completion of test objectives. The pack experienced end-of-discharge voltage divergence from about cycle 15,000 onward, and end-of-charge voltage divergence from about cycle 22,000 onward. The latter is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Individual cell end-of-charge voltages vs cycle number for Pack 6003A.

Pack 6006A

This pack was removed from testing after 21,601 cycles. The final C/D ratio was 1.05 at a V/T level of 7.5. The primary reasons for termination of testing were high end-of-charge voltages and completion of test objectives. The pack began to experience end-of-discharge voltage divergence from about cycle 5,000 onward and end-of-charge voltage divergence from about cycle 12,000 onward. These features are illustrated in a number of ways in Figures 10 through 13, shown below.

Figure 10. Pack 6006A: Min., max. and average cell end-of-charge and end-of-discharge voltages vs cycle number.

Figure 11. Individual cell end-of-charge voltages vs cycle number for Pack 6006A.

Figure 12. Pack 6006A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle number and time.

Figure 13. Pack 6006A: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time.

Advanced NiCd Cell Packs of Recent Manufacture

In order to assure the availability of reliable cell vendors for current and future NASA spacecraft, GSFC has obtained a number of recently manufactured cells from EPI. These cells have been of both the Super© NiCd design (Zircar/PBI separator, with electrolyte additive) and Magnum© design (Polypropylene separator). A sufficient number of 9, 10, 21 and 50 AH cells of both design types were obtained to build two test packs of each AH rating.

Acceptance testing of both Super© NiCd and Magnum© cells and batteries have exhibited anomalous capacity and voltage performance at low temperatures (-10 °C to 5 °C). Similar or related anomalies have been observed in LEO cycling at these temperatures, particularly when the DOD is shallow (15% or less). Consequently, it was decided to perform testing on one group of packs either at a particular mission profile or at low temperatures and a variable DOD profile as presented in Table II. The second group of packs would be subjected to an accelerated LEO test regime consisting of 90-minute orbits, 20 °C or 30 °C, 40% or 50% DOD, using NASA Standard V/T levels

Table II. EPI Advanced NiCd Cell Packs of Recent Manufacture on Life-cycle test at NSWC

NSWC Pack #	AH-Capacity, Design & Test Regime	Accelerated Pack #
0090B	9 AH Super© NiCd - 5 °C, 19 months of SAMPEX mission profile (0 - 18% DOD), then FAST ² mission profile (134-minute orbit, 12.5% DOD)	0090A ¹
6016F	21 AH Super© NiCd - 0 °C, SWAS ³ mission DOD limits (5% - 25%)	6015F ⁴
6106M	10 AH Magnum© - 0 °C, 2000 cycles each at 10, 25 & 50% DOD; repeat.	6122M ⁵
6506M	50 AH Magnum© - 0 °C, 2000 cycles each at 10, 25 & 50% DOD; repeat.	6522M ⁵
0106M	21 AH Magnum© - 0 °C, 2000 cycles each at 10, 25 & 50% DOD; repeat.	0121M ⁵

- 1 30 °C, 40% DOD
- 2 Fast Auroral Snapshot Explorer
- 3 Submillimeter Wave Astronomy Satellite
- 4 20 °C, 50% DOD
- 5 20 °C, 40% DOD

PACK 0090B

This pack began cycling in August of 1992. It has completed over 12,000 cycles to date; the first 7200 under the SAMPEX mission profile, the remainder under the FAST mission profile. One cell was removed from testing at the transition in orbital profiles, due to electrolyte leakage at the fill tube. A second cell, instrumented with a pressure transducer, began to exhibit voltage divergence on charge immediately after the transition. The divergence was most evident at beginning of charge. In concert with this divergence was a steady build-up of pressure over the next 2000 cycles. The pressure incrementally increased with each cycle (as trended at end-of-charge), and would *not* decrease during the subsequent discharge. To mitigate a possible transducer malfunction, the transducer was replaced, and the internal cell pressure was reset to 4 psia. Subsequently, this cell's charge voltage began to diverge again and the pressure also began to build up. Attempts to condition the pack by deep discharges of 50% DOD were a limited success. Voltage divergence would disappear for about 2 days, then progressively increase to the pre-conditioning value within a week. Pressure would *not* decrease during the 50% DOD conditioning, but would slowly decay about 10 psi over the succeeding 10 - 40

cycles. By the time the pack C/D ratio returned to pre-conditioning values, pressure again began to build, along with the voltage divergence. This behavior may be due, at least in part, to the limitations of the charge control algorithms presently available at NSWC.

Finally, Pack 0090B was reconditioned at cycle 11090 by discharging to 1.000 volt, followed by resistive let-down to approximately 0.010 V/cell. The capacity of this high charge-voltage cell was only about 5% less than the next lowest capacity cell. The pressure was reduced to about 3 psia at the completion of discharge. On the subsequent recharge, this cell peaked about 10 millivolts higher than the other 3 cells. The cells were then returned to the FAST-profile life-cycle testing. While pressure levels in this particular cell have since remained very low, the charge voltage has re-established its divergence signature. Figure 14 shows the profile *immediately following* reconditioning - at cycle 11,100. Figure 15 shows the individual cell voltage profiles at cycle 12,000, only 900 cycles later. This signature of voltage divergence is virtually identical to the signatures observed *prior* to reconditioning. The V/T level is now 0.040 V lower, but the magnitude of the divergence is the same.

Figure 14. Pack 0090B: Cell charge voltage profiles for cycle 11100.

Figure 15. Pack 0090B: Cell charge voltage profiles for cycle 12000.

PACK 6016F

This pack began cycling in January of 1995. It has completed over 3400 cycles to date, with DOD's randomly varying from 5% to 25%, per the test plan. Anomalous charge voltage divergence has been observed at almost every test point, but has been most significant at shallow DOD's. The most recent cycle (# 3400) is shown below in Figure 16, which shows individual cell voltages. The accelerated pack, 6015F, has not exhibited any appreciable charge voltage divergence to-date.

Figure 16. Pack 6016F: Cell charge voltage profiles for cycle 3400.

PACK 6106M

This pack began cycling in September of 1994. It has completed over 5800 cycles to date, with DOD's of 10% for the first 2000 cycles, then 25% DOD for the next 2000 cycles, and now 50% for another 2000 cycles. This pack has exhibited charge voltage divergence similar to Pack 6016F at 10% DOD. The divergence at 25% is about twice as great as at 10% DOD, and is greatest at 50% DOD. Figure 17 illustrates an overview of this divergence throughout the life-cycle testing to date. Figures 18 & 20 show the divergence profile vs cycle time for 25% and 50% DOD's respectively; and Figures 19 & 21 show the profiles of individual cell voltages at those DOD's. The accelerated pack, 6122M, has not exhibited any appreciable charge voltage divergence to-date.

Figure 17. Pack 6106M: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle number and time.

Figure 18. Pack 6106M: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time at 25% DOD.

Figure 19. Pack 6106M: Cell charge voltage profiles at 25% DOD.

Figure 20. Pack 6106M: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle time at 50% DOD.

Figure 21. Pack 6106M: Cell charge voltage profiles at 50% DOD.

PACK 6506M

This pack also began cycling in September of 1994. It has completed over 6100 cycles to date, with DOD's of 10% for the first 2000 cycles, then 25% DOD for the next 2000 cycles, and now 50% DOD for another 2000 cycles. This pack has exhibited charge voltage divergence similar to Pack 6106M at 10% DOD and 25% at DOD. However, unlike Pack 6106M, the divergence *disappears* at 50% DOD. Figure 22 illustrates an overview of divergence throughout the life-cycle testing to date. The accelerated pack, 6522M, has not exhibited any appreciable charge voltage divergence to-date.

Figure 22. Pack 6506M: Voltage divergence and current vs cycle number and time.

PACK 0106M

This pack began cycling in June of 1995. It has completed over 2200 cycles to date, with DOD's of 10% for the first 2000 cycles, presently 25% DOD for another 2000 cycles, to be followed by 50% DOD for another 2000 cycles. This pack has exhibited *no* appreciable charge voltage divergence to date. The accelerated pack, 0121M, has not exhibited any appreciable charge voltage divergence to date either.

Conclusions

Anomalous charge voltage behavior has been observed during life-cycle testing on both of the advanced NiCd cells (Super[®] NiCd & Magnum[®]) from EPI, particularly at cold temperatures (5 °C or less) and, to a certain extent, shallow DOD's (15% or less). This divergence may also be associated with accumulation of cell gasses and does not appear to be remedied by either deep discharges or total reconditioning. This divergence does not develop on any one cell at a predictable time, nor in a predictable manner.